

Multiterminal electrical charging station for LV networks

F.P. García-López, M. Barragán-Villarejo, *Member, IEEE*
J.M. Maza-Ortega, *Member, IEEE*, A. Gómez-Expósito, *Fellow, IEEE*
Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Sevilla.
Avda. De los Descubrimientos s/n, 41092 Sevilla, Spain
fdpgarcia@us.es, manuelbarragan@us.es, jmmaza@us.es, age@us.es

Abstract—The massive penetration of electric vehicles may create local problems on the LV distribution systems where the charging stations are located. Most of the solutions proposed in the specialized literature are based on centralized algorithms which are applied to traditional LV distribution systems. This paper proposes a new charging station based on a multiterminal DC-link. This new infrastructure allows to create a flexible link between the radial feeders which allows to maximize the use of the current assets and an optimized operation of the network by means of a MV/LV transformer equalization.

Index Terms—Electric Vehicle, Voltage Source Converters, LV distribution system, multiterminal DC-link.

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of electrical vehicles (EVs) as a new agent in distribution networks has been widely analyzed during the last years. On the one hand, a massive integration of EV may affect the demand curve of a power system depending on when the charge is done [1]. On the other hand, the impact of EVs on the local distribution system where the charging stations are connected completely modifies the power flows, voltage profile and losses of the system [2], [3]. For this reason, different charging strategies have been evaluated to mitigate the negative effects of the EVs. Most of these strategies are based on a centralized control algorithm which uses some measurements of the distribution network and the predictions of the EV power demand to compute an optimal pattern of EVs charging [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]. This solution can be applied in a smart grid environment with a communication infrastructure. However, all the aforementioned proposals to solve the local impact of EV charge considers a traditional scheme of the distribution network. This work proposes to modify the topology of LV distribution networks by introducing multiterminal DC-links to integrate the charge of EVs. This new topology of EV charging facility will bring a flexible operation of the LV network leading to an improve operation and network investment deferral.

II. BENCHMARK SYSTEM

The benchmark system used in the simulation is shown in Fig.1. This system considers a MV/LV transformer substation composed of two subsystems supplied by two transformers rated at 630 kVA and 20/0.4 kV. Each transformer supplies four feeders comprising a total of sixteen loads with different

daily profiles (including household, industrial and service loads). The complete parameters of lines are shown in Table I and the total daily active and reactive load profile for subsystems 1 and 2 at transformer heads are depicted in Fig. 2. Note that subsystem 2 is more loaded than subsystem 1. The daily profiles are fully explained in [9] for each type of load. In addition, an electrical vehicle charging station (EVCS) composed of eight fast charging point each rated at 50 kW is connected at buses 11, 12, 13 and 14. The daily charging profile of each bus is depicted in Fig. 3. It shows that buses connected to subsystem 2 (13 and 14) are more loaded than buses connected to subsystem 1 (11 and 12).

TABLE I
LINE PARAMETERS

	R (Ω /km)	X (Ω /km)	L (km)
Lines T1-1, T1-2, T1-3, T1-4	0.152	0.140	0.2
Lines T2-5, T2-6, T2-7, T2-8	0.152	0.140	0.2
Lines 1-9, 2-10, 3-11, 4-12	0.152	0.140	0.1
Lines 5-13, 6-14, 7-15, 8-16	0.152	0.140	0.1

Two case studied are considered in this work: base case (BC) and multiterminal DC-link. In the BC, the EVCS is fed radially from the buses mentioned above as it is shown in the top plot of Fig. 1. Each fast point charging is connected through a voltage source converter (VSC) [11] to its corresponding bus. In order to optimize the performance of the LV distribution system, it is proposed to create a flexible link (FL) between the radial feeders by means of a multiterminal DC-link [10]. This system allows controlling the active and reactive power flows between the interconnected feeders avoiding congestions and voltage problems when the EVCS is working. In this way, the FL improves the efficiency of the system and may even reduce the investments on networks assets required to cope with EVs. The proposed multiterminal DC-link is depicted in the bottom plot of Fig. 1. This is composed by a number of VSCs sharing a common DC bus and its AC side is connected to the LV network through LCL coupling filters [12]. Finally, the EVCS is connected into the common DC bus through DC/DC converter for each fast point charging.

Fig. 1. Top plot: Benchmark distribution system with the conventional EVCS (Base Case). Bottom plot: Benchmark distribution with the proposed EVCS (VSC Case).

III. ELECTRICAL VEHICLE CHARGING STATION CONTROL STRATEGY

The control strategy used to manage the EVCS is depicted in Fig. 4. This presents three control levels, which are hierarchically organized as follow:

A. Smart Meter Concentrator

The smart meter concentrator (SMC) is located in the MV/LV transformers substation. It collects voltage and current data from transformers T1 and T2 and computes the active power of both transformers, P_{T1} and P_{T2} . These powers are sent to the next control level with an update frequency of a few seconds.

B. Electrical Vehicle Management System

The Electrical Vehicle Management System (EVMS) is located into the multiterminal DC-link. This is in charge of

Fig. 2. Top plot: Benchmark distribution system with the conventional EVCS (Base Case). Bottom plot: Benchmark distribution with the proposed EVCS (VSC Case).c

Fig. 3. Top plot: Benchmark distribution system with the conventional EVCS (Base Case). Bottom plot: Benchmark distribution with the proposed EVCS (VSC Case).

generating the VSC active power references to the next control level from the data provided by the SMC. Its main objective is to balance the transformers load through the active power flow control between the interconnected feeders. Thus the risk of overloads due to load changes of the EV power demand can be reduced.

The control algorithm used for this system is depicted in

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the EVCS Control Strategy.

Fig. 5. This is based on PI controller where the input are the error sum between the active power references, P_{T1}^* and P_{T2}^* , and the active powers sent by the SMC, P_{T1} and P_{T2} . In this case, the references are computed from average value of P_{T1} and P_{T2} in order to balance the transformers load. The output from the controller is the total active power reference for VSCs connected to subsystem 2, VSC3 and VSC4. This is divided by two to assign the same active power reference for both converters, P_{VSC}^{3*} and P_{VSC}^{4*} . In addition to the PI controller, an extra block to consign the VSC2 active power reference is executed. This is based on the active power balance into the DC-link which is formulated as follow:

$$P_{VSC}^{1*} + P_{VSC}^{2*} + P_{VSC}^{3*} + P_{VSC}^{4*} + P_{EV} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where P_{EV} is the EVCS active power demand calculated using voltage v_{dc}^{EV} and current i_{dc}^{EV} . Defining the same power for VSC1 and VSC2, the active power reference for VSC2 is obtained as:

$$P_{VSC}^{2*} = -\frac{P_{VSC}^{3*} + P_{VSC}^{4*} + P_{EV}}{2} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the VSC active power references are determined. Note that VSC1 active power reference is not required because it is the balance VSC into the multiterminal DC-link. Its objective is to control the DC voltage in the common DC bus. Finally, it is important to point that a communication delay has been considered as the SMC and the EVMS are located in different places. This delay depends on the communication system to be implemented.

Fig. 5. Control strategy for the EVMS.

C. Inner Control Loop

The inner control loop (ICL) is also located in the multiterminal DC-link. It is in charge of tracking the active power references sent from EVMS, $P_{VSC}^{2*,3*,4*}$, as well as the DC voltage reference, v_{dc}^* , controlled by VSC1. Moreover, this control level will control the voltage level in the point of interconnection by means of the reactive power injection [10]. The control strategy is designed in a synchronous reference frame using a PI controller [13] for the current references. These are obtained from the power references [11] allowing to the controller computes the PWM signals to VSCs in order to obtain the desired values.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section is devoted to perform a complete day simulation considering the benchmark systems presented in section II. The main objective is to compare the current of the branches which are feeding the EVCS and the power of each MV/LV transformer. Fig. 6 shows the currents of two branches, I_{T2-5} and I_{T2-6} , and their ampacity limit, I_{rms}^{rat} , using the conventional and proposed EVCS. It can be observed that the feeders are overloaded in the BC in some instants whereas in the proposed scheme the currents are maintained within the limit thanks to the active power balance achieved by the VSCs. This behaviour can be also observed in Fig. 7,

Fig. 6. Current of branches T2-5 and T2-6 for the BC and VSC case.

where the apparent power of the transformers are shown. The top plot shows that the transformer 2 is overloaded around 20:00 when a high active power demand is required by the EVCS, P_{EV} . However, using the proposed scheme, which is represented in the middle plot, the active power of each transformer is maintained below the rated power. Note also that the proposed control strategy achieves an equalization of the transformer load leading to an operation with minimal

power losses. Finally, the bottom plot shows the active power flows of each VSC with the proposed control strategy.

Fig. 7. Top plot: Apparent power of each transformer for the BC. Middle plot: Active power of each transformer for the VSC case and active power demanded by the EVCS. Bottom plot: Injected active powers of the VSCs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has proposed the introduction of a new Electric Vehicle Charging Station (EVCS) based on a multiterminal DC-link. The aim of this device is to integrate a number of fast charging points in the LV distribution network minimizing their impact in terms of voltage profile and congestion of LV branches and MV/LV transformers. For this purpose, a hierarchical control management system (EVMS) based on local and MV/LV substation measurements has been proposed. The objective of this control algorithm is to achieve an equalization of the MV/LV transformers in order to minimize the losses of the system considering both the ampacity and voltage constraints of the network. A benchmark LV distribution system has been proposed to compare the classical charging station with the multiterminal DC-link approach. The results reveal that it is possible to improve the operation of the system because not only the congestions are avoided but also the transformer equalization is achieved.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank to the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness the financial support under the research project ENE2011-24137.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Hadley and A. Tsvetkova, "Potential impacts of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles on regional power generation," *Oak Ridge Nat. Lab., Oak Ridge, TN, Rep. ORNL/TM-2007/150*, Jan. 2008.
- [2] J.A.P. Lopes, F.J. Soares, P.M.R. Almeida, "Integration of Electric Vehicles in the Electric Power System," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol.99, no.1, pp. 168-183, Jan. 2011.

- [3] R. Vicini, O. Micheloud, H. Kumar, A. Kwasinski, "Transformer and home energy management systems to lessen electrical vehicle impact on the grid," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol.6, no.12, pp. 1202-1208, December 2012.
- [4] R. Faria, P. Moura, J. Delgado, A.T. de Almeida, "Managing the Charging of Electrical Vehicles: Impacts on the Electrical Grid and on the Environment," *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine*, vol.6, no.3, pp. 54-65, Fall 2014.
- [5] Kan Zhou, Lin Cai, "Randomized PHEV Charging Under Distribution Grid Constraints," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol.5, no.2, pp. 879-887, March 2014.
- [6] Shuang Gao, K.T. Chau, Chunhua Liu, Diyun Wu, C.C. Chan, "Integrated Energy Management of Plug-in Electric Vehicles in Power Grid With Renewables," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol.63, no.7, pp. 3019-3027, Sept. 2014.
- [7] Lunci Hua, Jia Wang, Chi Zhou, "Adaptive Electric Vehicle Charging Coordination on Distribution Network," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol.5, no.6, pp. 2666-2675, Nov. 2014.
- [8] L. Igualada, C. Corchero, M. Cruz-Zambrano, F.-J. Heredia, "Optimal Energy Management for a Residential Microgrid Including a Vehicle-to-Grid System," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol.5, no.4, pp. 2163-2172, July 2014.
- [9] C. Carmona-Delgado, E. Romero-Ramos, J. Riquelme-Santos, "Fast and reliable distribution load and state estimator," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 101, pp.110-124, Aug. 2013.
- [10] M. Barragan, J. M. Mauricio, A. Marano, M. Nieves, J. Churio, J. M. Maza-Ortega, E. Romero, and A. Gomez, "Operational benefits of multiterminal DC-links in active distribution networks," *Power and Energy Society General Meeting*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 22-26, July 2012.
- [11] A. Yazdani and R. Iravani, *Voltage-sourced Converters in Power Systems*. Wiley-Blackwell, 2010.
- [12] M. Liserre, F. Blaabjerg, and S. Hansen, "Design and control of an LCL-filter based three-phase active rectifier," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 1281-1291, Sept. Oct. 2005
- [13] D. Holmes, T. Lipo, B. McGrath, and W. Kong, "Optimized design of stationary frame three phase ac current regulators," *Power Electronics, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 24, no. 11, pp. 2417-2426, nov. 2009.